

ART AS A FACTOR OF AESTHETIC EDUCATION

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Annotation: *This article discusses the fact that art is the most important form of aesthetic approach to reality, its role in the aesthetic education of the younger generation.*

Keywords: *art, aesthetic education, social life, aesthetic culture, harmonious human being, universe, subject-object, aesthetic feeling, aesthetic taste, aesthetic dream.*

Among the means of aesthetic education, art plays an important role. Art is the most important form of aesthetic approach to reality. The level of aesthetic culture of a society depends in many respects on the level of development of art, how much it plays an important role in social life.

Civil society has set itself the goal of successfully solving the tasks related to the upbringing of a harmoniously developed person, the formation of a broad outlook, high morals, aesthetic culture. The scientific and technological revolution has made great changes not only in human life, but also in the system of their upbringing, revealing new aspects of the old problems in human education and making rational and emotional balance a very urgent problem. This includes the issue of seeing art as a unique tool of education.

In many works on the theory of aesthetic education (Plato, Aristotle, Schiller, Hegel, Russian revolutionary democrats, etc.) art is given such a place. Recent research on art and personality structure provides a new basis for a careful study of the distinctive features of art as an important tool in human education. The process of studying the impact of art on the individual requires the use of modern methods and approaches, including the idea of system and structure, in modeling two complex dynamic systems - the artistic image and some aspects of personality relationships.

In recent years, a number of researchers have begun to use the term “model” to describe the specific features of the depiction of an entity in art. For example, the German aesthetic scientist H. Redeker writes: creates a picture, similar to what literature shows in front of his eyes”[1].

Art assimilates the universe in its relation to man, in turn, the object of art, as a product of man's relation to the universe, manifests itself in all its clarity. These relationships are specific to the subject-object relationship, through which all aspects of

human activity take place. Analyzing the creative principles in the work of M. Gin Nekrasov, he made some interesting observations: "It's very difficult to separate each of them, to divide them into parts"[2].

Art uses all its means of artistic expression to convince people that the reality perceived through art is the same in real life. As Dostoevsky points out, in a real artist, the characters are "almost real." Emphasizing this feature, M.S. Kagan connects it with the specific features of art modeling existence. "Artistic imagery models," he writes, "unlike scientific models, do not simply interpret the universe, but rather coexist with the 'illusioned being' that exists and is so perceived by us"[3]. In art it is a peculiar form of illusion, in which the model itself is taken as an interchangeable object. At the same time, the acceptance of art by listeners, spectators and students always preserves a sense of norealism, the illusion of art models.

Art, as a means of aesthetic education, is aimed at each person, to form a sense of a broad and open view of the world, to directly observe the subtleties, to create creativity in the way of high dreams and hopes. If science serves to develop a person's professional activity, art develops his all-round natural ability, teaches him to perceive the world as a whole. While art also helps you get a career, it does help you get stuck in a narrow profession. Compared to other forms of social consciousness, art has a greater and more effective effect on the all-round, harmonious development of the human person.

As the most important means of aesthetic education, art involves not only the perception of artistic values, but also their creation. The active participation of members of society, especially the younger generation, in the creation of artistic values leads to the development of their aesthetic tastes and needs, the stimulation of creative abilities.

Aesthetic theory, which is the basis of aesthetic knowledge, is also of great importance in the system of means of aesthetic education. Aesthetic theory affects components of aesthetic consciousness such as aesthetic feeling, aesthetic taste, aesthetic desire. Aesthetic feeling, aesthetic taste, aesthetic desire are strengthened under the influence of aesthetic theory. A person's aesthetic views become his beliefs, expanding his scope of knowledge.

Aesthetic education can achieve the intended results and success only if it is based on the purpose, system of methods of general educational activity, the combination of external and internal factors in the formation of aesthetic culture of the individual, the specific features of educational activity. The system of aesthetic education leads to the expected results only when it is integrated in the family and school, production communities, ideological institutions, the media, cultural institutions, socio-political and public organizations. The interaction of family, school and educational institutions in aesthetic education also brings good results.

Aesthetic education is aimed at educating a socially active, versatile and harmoniously developed person. Further formation of the aesthetic consciousness of the citizens of the independent state of Uzbekistan is an urgent task of aesthetic education, which serves to further enhance the artistic culture of society, the further development of aesthetic needs and values.

It is possible to correctly understand the essence of this process on the basis of identifying the factors of aesthetic maturity of the person, understanding the nature of their interrelationship. In this sense, the factors that ensure the aesthetic maturity of an individual are diverse in terms of the mechanisms and nature of their influence on him.

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